

IMPROVING STUDENTS' ENGLISH VOCABULARY THROUGH SPELLING BEE IN THE SECOND GRADE IN OF MTs DDI TAKKALASI

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Abstract

This study aims to find out how spelling bee affects students' vocabulary acquisition and to describe how students perceive their vocabulary acquisition through spelling ability. This study used a quantitative method approach combined into an experimental group and a control group. Participants of this study involved 96 students (VIIIa1 – VIIIa4) of MTs DDI Takkalasi. The instruments used in this study were pre-test, post-test, and questionnaires. Data were analyzed using a formula and a Likert scale. The results of the study revealed that the application of spelling abilities in learning vocabulary can improve students' understanding significantly. This can be seen from the post-test average score of the students in the experimental class increased higher than the pre-test average score and the average score of students in the control class. The average score obtained in the experimental class at the pre-test was 83.40 in class VIIIa1 and 74.1 in class VIIIa2. While the average score obtained in the post-test was 93.88 in class VIIIa1 and 83.22 in class VIIIa2 which was higher in the pre-test score. Learning vocabulary using spelling bee was responded with agree by students in class VIIIa1 and responded neutrally by students in class VIIIa2. Spelling bee was applied effectively in learning and mastering vocabulary in class VIIIa1 and class VIIIa2. Therefore, learning vocabulary through spelling bee is very effective for students.

Keywords: Spelling Bee, English Vocabulary, Experimental Class, Control Class

1. INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary is one of the most crucial components of language literacy since it allows people to communicate ideas or concepts in spoken or written form. The need of vocabulary recognition must be emphasized from a young age. According to Kridalaksana (2001: 89) states that vocabulary is a wealth of words owned by a reader or writer of a language. In line with that statement, according to Nurgiyantoro (2001:146), vocabulary is vocabulary or whatever is owned by a language. On the other hand, vocabulary is a core component of language proficiency and provides much of the basis for how well students speak, listen, read and write (Richards & Renandya, 2002). To master a large vocabulary, it takes basic techniques or basic skills in pronunciation.

The most basic step in learning a language is spelling. Basic spelling is learned by all language users. According to Hasan Alwi (2002: 285), spelling is the rule of how to describe sounds (words, sentences, and so on) in written form (letters), as well as the use of punctuation marks. Spelling is the rules of how to describe the speech of a language. The ability to spell supports a person's reading ability. One of the basic things parents teach their children is spelling letters. Spelling letters is the first step in learning a language. Letters are the most important component in the spelling stage. Letters can also be interpreted as one of the sub-basics in learning a language. Spelling of letters is the basic component that is learned to compose a word, the word itself is then assembled into a sentence, that sentence is used to learn to speak or read. Spelling

has also become a basic requirement or requirement for learning English. However, spelling in learning English is still underestimated by some people because it is considered as something that does not need to be learned. In fact, there are still many language users, especially English, who also don't know how to spell letters fluently and correctly. This proves that ignoring trivial things like spelling in English can make language users mispronounce words or sentences. This can lead to misunderstandings between the language user or the interlocutor. Therefore, it is very important to teach the spelling of letters to children from an early age. Mastering spelling makes children able to master words with the help of spelling.

According to Nasmilah (2023) language learners require longer time to understand and comprehend the course material. The course material especially English course is learnt in different ways depends on each learners' ability. Nida, Harris, and Tarigan suggest that language skills have four components, namely: listening skills, speaking skills, reading skills and writing skills. Spelling material is also one of the materials that is often forgotten in learning English, considering that people's attention is generally focused on words, phrases, or sentences as a whole without paying attention to the aspects of spelling or spelling (Tarigan, 2009).

In this study, the students' mastery of English vocabulary is seen from their spelling ability. Good spelling skills can improve proper vocabulary mastery. It also helps the students in reading and writing correctly. Good spelling also avoids misspelling or commonly known as typo. Abbot, Berninger, and Fayol (2010) say that differences in ability individual spelling can be explained through the level of spelling words and the level of composition text. Therefore, the researcher plans to correct spelling errors and improve the students' spelling abilities to a better level. Because spelling mistakes lead to misinterpretations and cause misunderstandings between users of one language and users of other languages.

Learning spelling should be given since children are in elementary school. However, in recent years, learning English has been removed from the curriculum for elementary school levels. Therefore, there are some public schools that do not applied English subjects to their students. Therefore, the researcher plans to teach spelling material to grade 2 students at the junior high school level.

In learning English, it is very susceptible to spelling or writing errors. One letter difference can change the meaning of the word that is said or written. Moreover, there are some English words that are very difficult to write and pronounce for people who are not native English speakers. This also happens to students who are just starting to learn English or are familiar with English vocabulary. In fact, many of the junior high school students are still wrong and not fluent with proper spelling. There were even some disciples at the top level who weren't very fluent in spelling either. This is also evidenced by the finding of errors in their pronunciation and writing of English vocabulary. Errors and non-fluency like this cause communication problems for students, be they fellow students or students and teachers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Spelling Bee

The Collins Dictionary defines "spelling" as the capacity to spell words accurately, including an individual's attempts to do so. The Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines spelling as the process of accurately creating words from each letter and the capacity to spell. The word "spell" derives from the word "spel," which means to say or mention the letters one at a time in the Big Indonesian Dictionary. The ability to accurately spell a word with many letters is referred to as spelling. The meaning of spelling in Indonesian lays more attention on the pronunciation of letters, whereas the meaning in English emphasizes the creation of words and the proper arrangement of letters so that spelling. Reed in Ramdhini (2016:7) states that spelling is producing the correct orthographic representation of a written word. English words that are formed with the right letter placement often translate into written language.

Spelling is important for three reasons: Communication: spelling is an important component of communication. Literacy: spelling and reading skills are closely related and help develop overall literacy. According to Graham et al. in Kleinpaste (2014:1), researchers and educational experts disagree over the best ways to teach spelling, but they agree that the ability to spell well is crucial for communication. Spelling is ignored in the realm of teaching English because of the perspectives of teachers that place a higher priority on reading and writing abilities. Some findings show that spelling has a stronger contribution to reading than reading to spell in first- and second-year students (Cavarolas, et al. in Abbot, Berninger and Fayol, 2010, p. 282). Spelling has a strong role in supporting fluency in reading for students. Abbot, et al in Ramdhini (2016: 281) writing skills are also supported by spelling skills. Learning to write, that is, producing letters that can be read and spelled, and creating coherent texts for many specific assignments through the curriculum is a major task of children's education in schools in early and middle childhood. Someone who has good spelling skills will also have good writing skills.

Spelling Bee is a part of American culture for a long time. Spelling Bee participants have children who have learned to spell, usually in elementary and junior high schools. After the proclamation of independence of the United States, the first book of spells was written by Noah Webster, published by American Press. The United States Spellbook by Noah Webster is used as a spellbook in the modern sense and is a continuation of the spell bee. It is also very popular in rural areas. The Spelling Bee grew in popularity after Webster's death in 1843 (Monaghan, 1999). Spelling bee is used as a teaching method to learn vocabulary. Spelling Bee can be used as an alternative method in teaching and mastering vocabulary. Spelling Bee is an activity that can provide pleasure and convenience in its implementation. Spelling bee as a competition that asks contestants to spell words. Spelling Bee is also called Spelldown. Spelling Bee as a competition when a competitor who misspelled a word will be eliminated. Spelling Bee isn't just about memorizing and spelling letters of words. It is considered as a complicated thought process (Williams, 2008).

Vocabulary

In the large Indonesian dictionary, KBBI (Dekdikbud, 1996: 527), vocabulary is defined as, "vocabulary". The words used in a language or a certain field collectively constitute the vocabulary. The word vocabulary itself comes from the Latin word *vocabulum* which means "to name", "to call" or "name". The other definition is compilation of words and phrases with their definitions explained is called a vocabulary list. Vocabulary refers to a list or collection of words for a particular language or a list or collection of words that may be used by speakers of each language (Hatch & Brown, 1995). Kridalaksana in Tarigan (1994:446) states that vocabulary is (1) a language component that contains information about the meaning and use of words in language; (2) the wealth of words owned by a speaker, writer or a language; and (3) word lists arranged like a dictionary, but with brief and practical explanations. Other names for vocabulary include word stock, lexicon, and lexis. Grammar and vocabulary are equally important in English, but they are not the same. Grammar is understood to be grammar, whereas vocabulary is understood to be vocabulary. This is the distinction between the two. As said by Linse (2006) vocabulary is a collection of words that are known by someone. The statement explains that vocabulary is a collection of vocabulary that is known to someone. The definition of vocabulary is a whole word or vocabulary or term that refers to certain concepts possessed by a person or a language in an environment. The meaning of vocabulary is all the words contained in a language. Vocabulary is all available words, both active vocabularies used by readers and writers and passive vocabulary used by readers and listeners (Dowdowski, 1982: 1454). In fact, vocabulary is not only related to all the words in the dictionary, although there are several new vocabularies that are automatically entered and added to English. A context can also be demonstrated via vocabulary. In other words, language can be utilized to express certain meanings and contexts in phrases. The phrase "My brother is a doctor, so he has an outstanding medical vocabulary" is an illustration of this. Given that his brother is a doctor, the phrase "medical vocabulary" in this statement refers to vocabulary used in the field of medicine. Vocabulary is a crucial component of language since it is used in all four language skills—listening, speaking, reading, and writing. This assertion suggests that because vocabulary is essential to speaking, reading, and writing, it plays a significant role in a language. This implies that a person's limited vocabulary and speaking skills are closely related. According to the definition given above, vocabulary is all the words that are present in anything that is heard, spoken, read, or written that that individual is familiar with.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, a quantitative approach was implemented combined with the application of an experimental design involving two groups (experimental group and control group). Creswell (2012) states that the notion of experimental research methods is used when the researcher wants to know the causal effect between the independent and dependent variables. This means that researchers must be able to control all variables that will affect outcomes unless the independent variable (treatment) has been determined. The experimental group was carried out using the spelling ability method while the control group did not use the spelling ability method in its implementation.

The experimental design can be seen in the following table adapted from Gay (2006:255):

Table 3.1 Classification Score

GROUP	Pre-Test	Treatment	Post-Test
EG	O ₁	X ₁	O ₁
CG	O ₂	X ₂	O ₂

Which:

EG: Experimental Group

CG: Control Group

O₁: Pre-Test

O₂: Post-Test

X₁: The treatment using spelling bee method

X₂: Treatment without using spelling bee method

Before implementing the treatment, the researcher first gave a pre-test to each experimental group and control group. Likewise, at the end of implementing the treatment, a post-test was given to see the difference in the scores of the students.

Before starting the research, the researcher outlined her goals and objectives and requested consent from those students who served as a sample. The researcher actively participated in the learning process as both a teacher and a researcher to support students' capacity to grasp vocabulary through spelling bee. Before giving treatment, the researcher gave a pre-test (oral test) for both the experimental group and the control group to determine the ability of each student. After giving the pre-test, the students were taught directly by the researcher in each class. In the experimental group class, spelling bee was applied to the treatment. Whereas in the control group the vocabulary was taught as usual. This research was carried out for 6 meetings in each class group. Several games and practices like semi-competition were applied to this treatment in each class to support their ability in understanding the methods and material provided. At the end of the meeting, a post-test (oral test) was given to find out the ability of the students after receiving the vocabulary teaching treatment in each group class. Questionnaires were also distributed to students in the experimental group class to find out their perceptions of the treatment given.

Data analysis techniques from pre-test and post-test scores are calculated based on Depdiknas (2006:5-320) for both experimental group and control group in the following formula:

Scoring student answers from the pre-test and post-test using the following formula:

$$\text{Score} = \frac{\text{Student correct answer}}{\text{Total number of items}} \times 100$$

Classifying the scores of the students on the following criteria:

Table 3.2 Classification of the Scores

Score	Classification
91-100	Very good
81-90	Good
71-80	Fair
61-70	Poor
00-60	Very poor

Calculating the average score of the students using the following formula adapted from Sudjana (1989:45):

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\%$$

P: Percentage

f: Number of frequency

N: The number of students

The formula for calculating the average score adapted from Gay (2006:320) as follows:

$$X = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

X = Mean score

$\sum X$ = The total number of student's scores

N = The number of students

Calculating the standard deviation score of the students using the formula adapted from Gay (2006:321):

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{SS}{N-1}} \quad SS = \sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{N}$$

SS: Sum square

N: Number of subjects

SD: Standard deviation

Responses analysis of the questionnaires distributed to the experimental group class was calculated using *Likert scale*. The researcher calculated the data responses using percentage technique formula adapted from Sudjana (1989:45) as follows:

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\%$$

P = Percentage

f = Number of frequency

N = Number of samples

The classification of the perceptions of the students is as follows:

- a) Strongly agree
- b) Agree
- c) Undecided
- d) Disagree
- e) Strongly disagree

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

The score data percentage of students' pre-test in experimental group and control group classes are described in the table below:

Table 4.1: The mean score of the pre-test for the experimental group class and the control group class

No	Classification	Range	Frequency				Percentage			
			Pre-Test Experimental Group		Pre-Test Control Group		Pre-Test Experimental Group		Pre-Test Control Group	
			VIIIa1	VIIIa2	VIIIa3	VIIIa4	VIIIa1	VIIIa2	VIIIa3	VIIIa4
1	Very Good	91-100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Good	81-90	3	2		1	11,11%	7,40%	0	6,26%
3	Fair	71-80	9	3	4	2	33,33%	11,11%	15,39%	12,5%
4	Poor	61-70	14	14	13	5	51,85%	51,85%	50%	31,25%
5	Very Poor	00-60	1	8	9	8	3,70%	50%	34,61%	50%
Total			27	27	26	16	100	100	100	100

The table shows the comparison of scores between the experimental group and the control group in the pre-test. For the experimental group, there were 3 students (11.11%) from class VIIIa1 and 2 students (7.40%) from class VIIIa2 who were at a good level. There were 9 students (33.33%) from class VIIIa1 and 3 students (11.11%) from class VIIIa2 who were at the fair level. Furthermore, there are 14 students (51.85%) from both classes who are at the poor level. And at the very poor level there is 1 student (3.70%) from class VIIIa1 and 8 students (50%) from class VIIIa2.

For the control group class, only 1 student (6.26%) from class VIIIa4 was at the good level. There were 4 students (15.39%) from class VIIIa3 and 2 students (12.5%) from class VIIIa4 who were at the fair level. At the poor level, there are 13 students (50%) from class VIIIa3 and 5 students (31.25%) from class VIIIa4. And last, there are 9 students (34.61%) from class VIIIa3 and 8 students (50%) from class VIIIa4 who are at the very poor level. It can be concluded that the students in the experimental group and control group classes were on average at the poor level in doing the pre-test distributed by the researcher.

The score data percentage of students' post-test in experimental group and control group classes are described in the table below:

Table 4.2: The mean score of post - test for the experimental group class and the control group class

No	Classification	Range	Frequency				Percentage			
			Pre-Test Experimental Group		Pre-Test Control Group		Pre-Test Experimental Group		Pre-Test Control Group	
			VIIIa1	VIIIa2	VIIIa3	VIIIa4	VIIIa1	VIIIa2	VIIIa3	VIIIa4
1	Very Good	91-100	14	6	3	1	51,85%	22,22%	11,53%	6,25%
2	Good	81-90	5	10	5	3	18,51%	37,03%	19,23%	18,75%
3	Fair	71-80	8	3	3	9	29,62%	11,11%	11,53%	56,25%
4	Poor	61-70	0	8	15	3	0	29,62%	57,69%	18,75%
5	Very Poor	00-60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total			27	27	26	16	100	100	100	100

It can be seen that there are differences from the pre-test and post-test tables above between the experimental group class and the control group class. In the experimental group, there were 14 students (51.85%) from class VIIIa1 and 6 students (22.22%) from class VIIIa2 who were at the very good level. at the good level, there were 5 students (18.51%) from class VIIIa1 and 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa2. There were 8 students (29.62%) from class VIIIa1 and 3 students (11.11%) from class VIIIa2 felt at the fair level. Meanwhile, at the poor level, only 8 students (29.62%) came from class VIIIa2.

Whereas in the control group class, at the very good level there were 3 students (11.53%) from class VIIIa3 and only 1 student (6,255) from class VIIIa4. There were 5 students (19.23%) from class VIIIa3 and 3 students (18.75%) from class VIIIa4. Meanwhile at the fair level, there are 3 students (11.53%) from class VIIIa3 and 9 students (56.25%) from class VIIIa4. Finally, there were 15 students (57.69%) from class VIIIa3 and 3 students (18.75%) from class VIIIa4.

The mean score is calculated to compare the scores between the experimental group and the control group from the results of the students' pre-test scores. the average score is described in the table below:

Table 4.3 The mean score and standard deviation the sample of students' pre- test for the experimental group class and the control group class

Class	Mean Score	N	Standard Deviation
Experimental VIIIa1	83.4	27	29.56
Experimental VIIIa2	74.11	27	10.81
Control class VIIIa3	66.46	26	78.89
Control class VIIIa4	66.18	16	72.88

Data analysis in the table above illustrates the average post-test score between the experimental class and the control class. The average score in the experimental class was 93.88 (VIIIa1) and 83.22 (VIIIa2). While the average score in the control class was 76.61 (VIIIa3) and 72.81 (VIIIa4). The average score in the experimental class was higher than the average score in the control class. And the standard deviation results in the two groups showed a significant

difference. The standard deviation in the experimental class was 29.56 (VIIIa1) and 10.81 (VIIIa2) while in the control class it was 78.89 (VIIIa3) and 72.88 (VIIIa4).

Based on the response analysis table in statement number 1, there were 14 students (51.85%) from class VIIIa1 and 9 students (33.33%) from class VIIIa2 who claimed to strongly agree. 2 students (7.40%) from class VIIIa1 and 9 students (33.33%) from class VIIIa2 chose agree on statement number 1. In the neutral option, there were 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa1 and 8 students (29.62%) students from class VIIIa2. And in each of the two classes, there was 1 student (3.70%) who marked the disagree option in statement number 1. It can be seen that most of the students are interested in using spelling bee in learning English vocabulary. For statement number 2, there were 12 students (44.44%) from class VIIIa1 and 7 students (25.92%) from class VIIa2 who claimed the strongly agree option. 5 students (18.51%) from class VIIIa1 and 14 students (51.85%) from class VIIIa2 marked agree as their option. and in the neutral option, there were 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa1 and 6 students (22.22%) from class VIIIa2. This concludes that students especially in class VIIIa2 enjoy learning vocabulary using spelling bee. The results of the responses to statement number 3 show that there were 12 students (44.44%) from class VIIIa1 and 7 students (25.92%) from class VIIIa2 who placed their choice on strongly agree. There were only 9 students (33.33%) from class VIIIa2 who claimed to agree. In neutral option, 11 students (40, 74%) from VIIIa1 and 10 students (37, 03%) from VIIIa2. There were 4 students (14.81%) from class VIIIa1 and only 1 student (3.70%) from class VIIIa2 who chose disagree. In response to statement number 3, it can be seen that the average student is neutral with the statement applying spelling bee can make it easier to remember new vocabulary. For the response results from statement number 4, there were 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa1 and 4 students (14.81%) from class VIIIa2 who placed their choices to strongly agree. In the agree choice, there were 6 students (22.22%) from class VIIIA1 and 15 students (55.55%) from class VIIIA2. 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa1 and 7 students (25.92%) from class VIIIa2 who made their choices in neutral options. And in the disagree choice, there was only 1 student (3.70%) from both classes. It is clear that the average student agrees with statement number 4 that applying spelling bee can make me more active in class. The results of statement number 5 show that there are 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa1 and 6 students (22.22%) from class VIIIa2 who marked strongly agree. There were 2 students (7.40%) from class VIIIa1 and 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa2 who confirmed that they agree. 14 students (51.85%) from class VIIIa1 and 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa2 voted neutral. Only 1 student (3.70%) from class VIIIa1 chose disagree. And finally, there were 2 students (7.40%) from class VIIIa1 and only 1 student (3.70%) from class VIIIa2 who chose strongly disagree. In statement number 5, the students dominated the neutral choice to be motivated to learn a lot of new vocabulary through spelling bee. The response to statement number 6 shows that 10 students (37.03%) from VIIIa1 and 6 students (22.22%) from VIIIa2 confirmed strongly agree. There were 2 students (7.40%) from class VIIIa1 and 11 students (40.74%) from class VIIIa2 indicated agree. In the neutral option, 14 students (51.85%) from class VIIIa1 and 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIa2. And only 1 student (3.70%) from class VIIIa1 marked disagree. it can be seen that the students dominated the undecided option in statement number 6. For statement number 7 there were 12 students

(44.44%) from class VIIIA1 and 9 students (33.33%) from class VIIIA2 who stated that they strongly agree. 4 students (14.81%) from class VIIIA1 and 12 students (44.44%) from class VIIIA2 agreed as their choice. and in the neutral option there were 11 students (40.74%) from class VIIIA1 and 6 students (22.22%) from class VIIIA2. This concludes that the strongly agree option was voted on by students from both classes regarding statement number 7. Based on the responses analysis table in statement number 8 above, there were 8 students (29.62) from class VIIIA1 and 5 students (18.51%) from class VIIIA2 who strongly agreed. 6 students (22.22%) from class VIIIA1 and 13 students (48.14%) from class VIIIA2 chose to agree with statement number 8. In the neutral choice there were 11 students (40.74%) from class VIIIA1 and 8 students (29.62%) students from class VIIIA2. And in class VIIIA1 there were 2 students (7.40%) and 1 student (3.70%) from class VIIIA2 who marked the choice to disagree in statement number 8. It can be seen that there is an equal number between the choices strongly agree and agree claimed by the students to statement number 8. The results of statement number 9 show that there were 13 students (48.14) from class VIIIA1 and 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIA2 who strongly agreed. There was 1 student (3.70%) from class VIIIA1 and 8 students (29.62%) from class VIIIA2 who agreed. 9 students (33.33%) from class VIIIA1 and 7 students (25.92%) from class VIIIA2 chose neutral. And respectively in the Disagree and Strongly Disagree options, there were 2 students (7.40%) from class VIIIA1 and only 1 student (3.70%). It is clear that the responses to statement number 9 are dominated by the strongly agree option. The results of the last statement number 10 show that there are 9 students (33.33%) from class VIIIA1 and 6 students (22.22%) from class VIIIA2 who chose strongly agree. There were 5 students (18.51%) from class VIIIA1 and 15 students (55.55%) from class VIIIA2 who claimed agree option. 10 students (37.03%) from class VIIIA1 and 4 students (14.81%) from class VIIIA2 chose neutral. And in the disagree options, there were 2 students (7.40%) from class VIIIA1 and only 1 student (3.70%) from VIIIA2 class. Finally, in the strongly disagree option, there is only 1 student (3.70%) from both classes. It is clear that the responses to statement number 10 are dominated by the agree option.

Discussion

The first objective discussed in this study is to find out how spelling bee affects students' vocabulary acquisition. Using spelling bee in learning vocabulary can significantly influence the development of students' understanding of vocabulary. Pre-test and post-test were administered to students in both the experimental group and the control group to find out the differences in students' scores and understanding before and after giving treatment. The provision of exercises in the form of games about spelling was also carried out by researchers to support the students' bee to get used to the spelling method being taught. The students in the experimental group class were given a pre-test, treatment, exercise while playing games, and post-test during the research phase. The difference in scores between the experimental group and the control group in the pre-test can be seen in the description of the table description of the average score of the students. The comparison between the students' mean scores of the experimental group (VIIIA1 and VIIIA2 class) on the post-test was higher than the scores of pre - test. 93.88 (VIIIA1) and 83.22 (VIIIA2) from the experimental group class. While 76.61 (VIIIA3) and 72.81 (VIIIA4) from the control group class. And the results of the standard

deviation in the two groups showed further differences. 29.56 (VIIIa1) and 10.81 (VIIIa2) from the experimental group class while 78.89 (VIIIa3) and 72.88 (VIIIa4) from the control group class. Students' perceptions regarding the treatment of learning and understanding of English vocabulary using the spelling bee method. The analysis of student achievement can also be seen from the response data on the questionnaires that have been distributed after giving the treatment. Questionnaires were administered only in the experimental group class (VIIIa1 and VIIIa2). The students in the experimental class have received vocabulary learning with spelling ability techniques. The total data results were obtained from the analysis using the formula from Sudjana (1989:45) and the Likert scale formula. To produce a total data set, the researcher analyzed the responses to the statements in each item. The findings of the response analysis result from the questionnaires of students in class VIIIa1 showed the highest ranking in the answers strongly agree with the total responses of 110 (407.41%). 33 (122.22%) the total responses to the answer agree. In neutral answers with a total response of 109 (403.70%). 14 (51.85%) total answers to disagree responses and 5 (18.51%) total answers to strongly disagree responses. Whereas in class VIIIa2 it showed a total of 69 (255.55%) responses to strongly agree, 116 (429.63%) to agree responses, 86 (318.52%) to neutral responses, 6 (22.22%) to disagree responses, and finally 3 (11.11%) to strongly disagree responses.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusions

Based on the findings and discussion of the analysis in chapter IV, it is concluded that spelling bee is proven as an easy and fun method or way to use in learning vocabulary and increasing the average score of students. The average score obtained in the experimental class at the pre-test was 83.40 in class VIIIa1 and 74.1 in class VIIIa2. While the average score obtained in the post-test was 93.88 in class VIIIa1 and 83.22 in class VIIIa2 which was higher in the pre-test score. It means that there is a more significant difference in the achievement of scores and the understanding of students who were in the experimental class (learning vocabulary using spelling bee) and the control class (learning vocabulary without using spelling bee).

The findings of the questionnaire of this research which have supported spelling bee as a method in facilitating students on mastering and understanding vocabulary. In the answers strongly agree with the total responses of 110 (407.41%). 33 (122.22%) the total responses to the answer agree. In neutral answers with total responses of 109 (403.70%). 14 (51.85%) total answers to disagree responses and 5 (18.51%) total answers to strongly disagree responses. In class VIIIa2 it showed a total of 69 (255.55%) responses to strongly agree, 116 (429.63%) to agree responses, 86 (318.52%) to neutral responses, 6 (22.22%) to disagree responses, and finally 3 (11.11%) to strongly disagree responses. It can be concluded that learning vocabulary using spelling bee is responded with agree by students in class VIIIa1 and responded neutrally by students in class VIIIa2. Spelling bee was applied effectively in learning and mastering vocabulary in class VIIIa1 and class VIIIa2.

Suggestions

In teaching and learning vocabulary using spelling ability, the researcher proposes the following suggestions:

1) For the teacher

Since the researcher implemented and proved that the use of spelling bee contributes effectively in teaching vocabulary. Teachers especially teachers in English subjects are highly recommended to use this method for teaching the students because this method is very easy and interesting to apply in teaching vocabulary.

2) For the further researchers

The researcher expects that the findings from this study will be used as a starting point for similar problems or research in the future.

3) General suggestion

Spelling bee must be mastered in advance at the beginning of learning English so that it makes it easier for students to master other steps in English material. Teachers also have to motivate students to be more aware in learning English.

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